

WHITE BEAR SUPPRESSION AND SELF ESTEEM OF STUDENTS IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION

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White Bear Suppression and Self Esteem of Students in Relation to Academic Achievement: Basis for Intervention

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between students' academic achievement, self-esteem, and White Bear Suppression. A descriptive research method was used in this study. This study utilized a sample of 177 Grade 11 students as respondents. A standardized data gathering instrument which was adopted from the White Bear Suppression Inventory of Daniel M. Wegner & Sophia Zanakos (1994) and Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale of Morris Rosenberg (1979). The result showed that the Grade 11 Students of Tabao National High School have high level of White Bear Suppression, have low self-esteem, and have an outstanding academic achievement. It also showed that there was a significant relationship between the White Bear Suppression and academic achievement while no significant relationship was found between self-esteem and academic achievement.

Keywords: *white bear suppression, self esteem, academic achievement, students*

Introduction

Academic achievement may be defined as the accomplished success in any educational task or an individual's ability to reach a set goal through effort, skill, or courage within the school context (Sideridis & Alamri, 2023). Academic achievement is a critical factor in students' future academic and professional careers since it is usually closely linked to successful university entrance or job success. Academically successful individuals are more likely to be accepted to more prestigious educational institutions, have better employment opportunities, earn a high income, and experience high life satisfaction (Liu et al, 2020; Sideridis & Alamri, 2023). An essential academic construct in the course of education is self-esteem (Tus, 2020).

On the other hand, self-esteem is defined as sense of self-worth and self-respect, being crucial for understanding people's well-being and success (Monteiro et al., 2022). It is self-assessment; this perception and evaluation can be positive or negative and pleasant or unpleasant (Noronha et al., 2018).

Meanwhile, suppression of unwanted thoughts may increase these thoughts, leading to stress and anxiety. The White Bear Suppression Inventory is a survey to assess thought suppression. In fact the White Bear Suppression Inventory has been correlated with other scales that measure intrusive thoughts as well as depression and anxiety (Nabors et al., 2022).

However research on factors affecting students' achievement in mathematics has often neglected the impact of psychological variables, such as emotional intelligence, self-esteem, and self-efficacy (Ugwuanyi et al., 2020). The school must be able to create a social environment in order to foster better mental wellbeing and quality of life among its students (Cleofas, 2020), it is important to ensure that they are provided with proper care and treatment (Estrada et al., 2020).

These concerns led the researcher to determine the White Bear suppression and self-esteem of students in relation to academic achievement.

Research Questions

This study assessed the level of White Bear Suppression, self-esteem, and academic achievement in General Mathematics of Senior High School students of Tabao National High School in the District of Valladolid, Division of Negros Occidental in the School Year 2023 – 2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of White Bear Suppression of Grade 11 students?
2. What is the level of self-esteem of Grade 11 Students?
3. What is the academic achievement of Grade 11 students in general mathematics?
4. Is there a significant relationship between White Bear Suppression and academic achievement in General Mathematics of Grade 11 students of Tabao National High School?
5. Is there a significant relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in General Mathematics of Grade 11 students of Tabao National High School?

Literature Review

According to the study of Tutgun-Ünal & Tarhan (2023), thought suppression is not easy, whether a person is trying not to think about a negative event or trying to avoid thinking. The person who wants to get rid of this intrusive thought repeats them over and over again. This can become an obsession in the process.

The research conducted by Robinson (2022) suggests that a way in which people with lower self-esteem can begin appreciating the importance of having higher self-esteem. It involves considering how they may feel about the things they value in their lives. Laveena D'Mello (2018) mention that a satisfaction of self-esteem needs generates feelings and attitudes of self-confidence, self-worth, capacity and the feeling of being useful and necessary in the world

The study of Suleiman (2023) stated that it is widely agreed in all nations that education is the foundation of human understanding and success. Every nation's success and prosperity depend on its level and quality of education.

According to the study of Wang et al. (2020), people who regularly experience unwanted intrusive thoughts, thought intrusions can interfere with attention and executive functioning and impair performance on everyday tasks. According Göbel & Niessen (2021) the successful suppression of interfering thoughts in everyday (working) life is supposedly associated with several positive outcomes, such as better task focus and emotion regulation

Moreover, Göbel & Niessen (2021) stated that thinking too much about threatening or negative issues leads to increased accessibility of negative memories and thus to an increase in negative or even depressed mood. It has also been shown to reduce problem solving effectiveness and to decrease self-esteem.

The study of Moreno et al. (2022) posited that participants who have positive performance-relevant thoughts are more likely to do well on a variety of academic tasks than those who have neutral or negative thoughts.

According to Alghamdi et al. (2023), one factor that can negatively impact self-esteem is the experience of imposter syndrome, characterized by feelings of inadequacy and a persistent fear of being exposed as a fraud, despite evidence of competence.

In addition, Subon et al. (2020) claimed that self-esteem plays an important role in determining academic achievement and for students who obtained high achievement in their studies, the confidence level is higher than those who attained less because the latter are disadvantaged by their lack of self-confidence. Academic performance depends on their self-esteem and current relationships.

Tadese et al. (2022) asserted that academically successful students have higher self-esteem and self-confidence, low levels of anxiety and depression, are socially inclined, and are less likely to engage in substance abuse. Students who had good academic achievements have higher income, better employment benefits, and more advancement opportunities

The research data of Filippello et al. (2019) cited in Zhao et al. (2021) found that self-esteem can predict a person's level of academic engagement.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive – correlation research design. Descriptive design was used to describe the level of thought suppression, self-esteem, and academic achievement in General Mathematics of Grade 11 students when taken as a whole. It also used correlational design to determine the significant relationship among thought suppression, self-esteem, and academic achievement in General Mathematics of Grade 11 students of Tabao National High School. Correlation can demonstrate relationship between two or more variables. However, it cannot prove that changing one variable will affect the other (Cherry, 2023).

Respondents

The subject and respondents of this study were the Grade 11 Senior High School Students of Tabao National High School, District of Valladolid, Division of Negros Occidental in the School Year 2023-2024.

The Grade 11 Senior High School students of Tabao National High School in the District of Valladolid has a population of 317 students. The researcher used the Slovin's Formula to get the sample size of 177.

In determining the number of respondents, simple random sampling technique was utilized followed by the lottery method in order to identify the Grade 11 Senior High School student's respondents.

Instrument

The study utilized a standardized data gathering instrument, the use of White Bear Suppression Inventory of Daniel M. Wegner & Sophia Zanakos (1994) as cited in Nabors et al. (2022) and Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale of Morris Rosenberg (1979).

The White Bear Suppression Inventory comprised of fifteen (15) item questions and was used to gauge one's ability to suppress thoughts. The scoring of the WBSI was based on a 5-point scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). Higher scores on the WBSI indicate greater tendencies to suppress thoughts.

The 10-item Roseberg self-esteem scale was used to gauge one's level of self-esteem. A method of combining ratings was used for scoring, giving "strongly disagree" 1 point, "disagree" 2 points, "agree" 3 points, and "strongly agree" 4 points. Items 2, 5, 6, 8, 9 were reversely scored. Higher scores indicate higher self-esteem.

Procedure

The researcher sought permission from Tabao National High School's principal to conduct a study on “White Bear Suppression and Self-Esteem of Students in Relation to Academic Achievement: Basis for Intervention”. Upon approval, the researcher arranged the schedule of assessment with the class advisers and the researcher conducted the assessment to the Grade 11 students. After gathering the data, the researchers used the statistical methods required to address the study questions, to tabulate and assess the results.

Ethical Considerations

This study upholds ethical standards by ensuring participants provide informed consent, with minors requiring guardian approval, and by clearly explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and voluntary nature. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained through secure data handling and the use of unique identifiers. To protect respondents' psychological well-being, tasks were designed to minimize distress, and support resources were available if needed. The study strived for inclusivity by recruiting a diverse sample and respecting respondents' autonomy in disclosing personal information. An institutional ethics review board oversee compliance with ethical protocols, and a thorough debriefing was provided to clarify the study's purpose and findings. Data were used responsibly and findings reported transparently, ensuring integrity and avoiding bias or over generalization.

Results and Discussion

Level of White Bear Suppression of Grade 11 Students

The table presents the level of White Bear Suppression of Grade 11 students of Tabao National High School in the school year 2023 – 2024.

Table 1. *Level of White Bear Suppression of Students*

<i>Level of White Bear Suppression</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very High	42		
High	87		
Moderate	22	3.63	High
Low	9		
Very Low	17		
Total	177		

Table 1 shows that 42 respondents have very high suppression, 87 have high suppression, 22 have moderate suppression, 9 have low suppression, and 17 of them have very low suppression. The mean score of 3.63 interpreted as high suppression.

This reflects that the respondents engage in significant efforts to suppress unwanted thoughts. They have a high cognitive control mechanism characterized by the conscious and intentional effort to prevent specific thoughts or mental content from entering conscious awareness. They always try to put problems out of mind, often do things to distract self from unwanted thoughts, and stay themselves busy just to keep thoughts from intruding their mind.

This finding confirms to the study of Tutgun-Ünal & Tarhan (2023) that thought suppression is not easy, whether a person is trying not to think about a negative event or trying to avoid thinking. The person who wants to get rid of this intrusive thought repeats them over and over again. This can become an obsession in the process.

Level of Self-Esteem of Grade 11 Students

The table on the next page presents the level self-esteem of Grade 11 students.

Table 2. *Level of Self-Esteem of Students*

<i>Level of Self - Esteem</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very High	0		
High	35		
Low	136	2.28	Low
Very Low	6		
Total	177		

Based on Table 2, there were 35 respondents have a high self-esteem, 136 have low self-esteem, and 6 of them have a very low self-esteem. As a whole, the students' self-esteem has a mean score of 2.28 which indicates that they have a low self-esteem.

The result implies that students struggle with feelings of inadequacy, self-doubt, or negative self-perception. They are not satisfied with themselves, feel they do not have much to be proud of, feel useless at times, have less respect for themselves, inclined to think that they are a failure, and a negative attitude toward themselves.

The result agrees to Robinson (2022) who suggests that a way in which people with lower self-esteem can begin appreciating the importance of having higher self-esteem. It involves considering how they may feel about the things they value in their lives. Laveana

D'Mello (2018) mention that a satisfaction of self-esteem needs generates feelings and attitudes of self-confidence, self-worth, capacity and the feeling of being useful and necessary in the world.

Academic Achievement of Grade 11 Students

The table below shows the academic achievement of 11 students.

Table 3. *Level of Academic Achievement of Student*

<i>Level of Academic Performance</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Outstanding	124		
Very Satisfactory	36		
Satisfactory	11	90.42	Outstanding
Fairly Satisfactory	4		
Did Not Meet Expectation	2		
Total	177		

In Table 3, the mean score of the 124 respondents is 90.42 which is interpreted as outstanding. There are 124 respondents who have an outstanding academic achievement, 36 have very satisfactory, 11 have satisfactory, 4 of them have fairly satisfactory and 2 did not meet expectations.

The findings implies that the students have the ability to complete their educational work successfully and have the capacity to attain their goal in General Mathematics by skill, bravery, or effort.

The result supports that study of Suleiman (2023) it is widely agreed in all nations that education is the foundation of human understanding and success. Every nation's success and prosperity depends on its level and quality of education.

Relationship between White Bear Suppression and Academic Achievement

The table below illustrates the relationship between White Bear Suppression and academic achievement of Grade 11 students.

Table 4. *Relationship between White Bear Suppression and Academic Achievement*

<i>Level of White Bear Suppression</i>	<i>Level of Academic Achievement</i>					<i>Total</i>
	<i>Outstanding</i>	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	<i>Satisfactory</i>	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	<i>Did not meet Expectation</i>	
Very High	36	4	1	1	0	42
High	63	15	5	3	1	87
Moderate	13	6	3	0	0	22
Low	4	4	0	0	1	9
Very Low	8	7	2	0	0	17
Total	124	36	11	4	2	177

Computed value (G): 0.39

P-value: <0.001

Decision: Reject Ho

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

As shown in Table 4, out of 177 respondents, there are 87 of them who got a high level of White Bear Suppression and 9 of them have low level of White Bear Suppression. Out of the 87 who have a high level of White Bear Suppression, 63 of them have an outstanding academic achievement and 1 did not meet expectation. Out of 9 students who have a low level of White Bear Suppression, 4 of them have an outstanding and also 4 of students have a very satisfactory academic achievement and 1 did not meet expectation.

After computing the Goodman-Kruskal's Gamma or Gamma Coefficient, the computed value (G) is 0.39 with a P-value of <0.001. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and this means that there is a significant relationship between White Bear Suppression and the academic achievement.

This implies that White Bear Suppression is significantly related to academic achievement. Those who have a positive thought can attain a desired outcome, having negative thoughts like focusing on worries, self-handicapping, etc., is often associated have a reduced academic performance.

The result of this study supports the findings of Wang et al. (2020) that people who regularly experience unwanted intrusive thoughts, thought intrusions can interfere with attention and executive functioning and impair performance on everyday tasks. The successful suppression of interfering thoughts in everyday (working) life is supposedly associated with several positive outcomes, such as better task focus and emotion regulation (Göbel & Niessen, 2021).

Relationship between Self-Esteem and Academic Achievement

The table below presents the relationship between self - esteem and academic achievement of Grade 11 students of Tabao National High School, School Year 2023-2024.

Table 5. Relationship Between Self-Esteem and Academic Achievement

Level of Self-Esteem	Level of Academic Achievement					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not meet Expectation	
Very High	0	0	0	0	0	0
High	26	5	3	1	0	35
Low	93	30	8	3	2	136
Very Low	5	1	0	0	0	6
Total	124	36	11	4	2	177

Computed value (G): 0.03

P-value: 0.863

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance

As shown in Table 5, of the 177 respondents, 136 of them have a low level of self-esteem and 6 of them have a very low level of self-esteem. Out of the 136 students who have a low level of self-esteem, 93 of them have an outstanding academic achievement and only 2 of them did not meet expectation. Of the 6 respondents who have a very low level of self-esteem, 5 of them have an outstanding academic achievement and 1 has a very satisfactory academic achievement.

Using the Goodman-Kruskal's Gamma or Gamma Coefficient, the computed value (G) is 0.03 with a P-value of 0.863. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and this means that there is no significant relationship between self-esteem and the academic achievement.

This implies that self-esteem is not significantly related to academic achievement. Students can perform academically regardless of the level of their self-esteem.

This finding supports the cross-sectional study carried out at Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University (PNU) (2019). It states that there is a weak relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement. According to Alghamdi et al. (2023), one factor that can negatively impact self-esteem is the experience of imposter syndrome, characterized by feelings of inadequacy and a persistent fear of being exposed as a fraud, despite evidence of competence.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusion are formulated:

The Grade 11 students have low belief of themselves.

The Grade 11 students have high tendency to suppress their unwanted thoughts.

The Grade 11 students have an outstanding academic achievement.

As thought suppression increases, so does academic performance. Students who are better able to suppress unwanted thoughts are more successful academically.

Self-esteem and academic achievement appear to be independent variables. This means that changes in one do not necessarily result in changes in the other.

Student's self-esteem does not necessarily predict their academic achievement. High self-esteem does not guarantee high academic achievement, and conversely, low self-esteem does not inevitably lead to poor academic performance

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are put forward for consideration:

Curriculum development can be enhanced by adding knowledge of psychological concepts like self-esteem and white bear suppression. Supervisors have the ability to incorporate tools and activities that are designed to increase self-worth, encourage constructive thought patterns, and lessen the cognitive strain brought on by suppressing thoughts. Psychological barriers can be lessened by interventions like group counseling, adaptive learning technologies, or individualized tutoring, which can create an atmosphere that is more favorable for academic progress.

School administrators can modify current policies and programs by having a better understanding of the relationship between academic achievement, self-esteem, and the White Bear Suppression Inventory (WBSI). To establish a more complete and encouraging learning environment, this may entail incorporating psychological support mechanisms into the extracurricular activities, counseling services, and curriculum of the school.

Teachers to tailor interventions can provide extra support and establish a caring environment that attends to the individual psychological needs of learners, ultimately resulting in a more positive and conducive learning environment. Teachers can help foster a healthy classroom culture that prioritizes students' emotional well-being in addition to academic accomplishment by incorporating the study's findings into their instructional strategies. Creating a supportive environment where they feel understood, appreciated, and encouraged.

Students may establish a learning environment that improves concentration, motivation, and academic performance by actively

interacting with the study's findings and putting tactics to manage thought suppression and boost self-esteem into practice. As they realize that healthy coping mechanisms and a positive self-image support both academic success and a balanced, meaningful life, students can place a high priority on their mental and emotional well-being.

To establish a more encouraging learning environment, future studies might investigate how the findings can be incorporated into teacher preparation programs, curriculum creation, and educational regulations. A more comprehensive understanding can be attained by looking into potential cross-cultural and socioeconomic variations in the link between academic achievement, self-esteem, and white bear suppression. This information may be crucial for modifying interventions to fit particular socioeconomic and cultural settings. Future researchers can investigate how technology-mediated approaches, like educational apps or online platforms, may affect the dynamics between academic accomplishment, self-esteem, and white bear suppression given how education is changing and how much technology is used.

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